

COPING MECHANISMS OF GRADE 10 JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL LEARNERS TO SEDENTARY LIFESTYLE IN THE POST- COVID 19 PANDEMIC: BASIS FOR RECREATIONAL ACTIVITY PLAN

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ABSTRACT

The coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic continues to pose profound challenges to society even its post effects. Its spread has been mitigated through strategies including social distancing; however, this may result in the adoption of a sedentary lifestyle. This study aimed to investigate: physical activity (PA) levels, sedentary behavior (SB), and sleep in young adults during the COVID-19 epidemic, and the change in these behaviors after the pandemic. A total of 192 Grade 10 Learners participated in the cross-sectional study and completed a one-off online survey relating to general information, PA, SB, and sleep. For the longitudinal study, PA, SB, and sleep data, obtained from 192 participants after the COVID-19 pandemic, were analyzed. Participants engaged in low PA, high SB, and long sleep duration after the COVID-19 pandemic. Moreover, a significant decline in PA while an increase in time spent in both SB and sleep was observed after the COVID-19 outbreak. The results of this study demonstrated a sedentary lifestyle in Grade 10 learners after the COVID-19 pandemic, which will assist health policymakers and practitioners in the development of population specific health education and behavior interventions during this pandemic and for other future events and serve as a basis for recreational activity plan.

Keywords: *COVID-19, Physical Activity, Sedentary Behavior, Sleep, Grade 10 Learners*

INTRODUCTION

The disruptive effects of the COVID-19 pandemic have been felt worldwide across many demographics, sectors, and institutions. The Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic has led to more than 100 countries implementing various forms of restriction measures during 2020 (Dunford et al., 2020). Social distancing, travel restrictions, curfews, and school closures have been combined with hygienic efforts to slow the spread of COVID-19.

Modeling studies have reported that these public health measures are important to reduce virus incidence and mortality, and may proceed into 2022 (Kissler et al., 2020; Nussbaumer-Streit et al., 2020). While effective, the social and economic impacts of lockdowns may have negative consequences for psychological health. Excessive quarantining is linked to symptoms of depression, anxiety, irritability, and insomnia (Brooks et al., 2020). Factors such as boredom, misinformation, supply concerns, frustration, and financial loss are stressors that trigger a change in mood state and may also lead to a decline in mental health (Brooks et al., 2020). Survey results among individuals from pre and during the pandemic reported a three-fold increase in depression, and those with lower social and economic resources had higher levels of depression (Ettman et al., 2020). These are all correlated with increased suicidal ideations, particularly amid Covid-19 lockdowns (Chen et al., 2020).

Of particular concern are University and college students, who have been faced with the stress of remote learning and rapid life adjustments due to COVID-19-related restrictions (Husky et al., 2020; Sahu, 2020). A small survey of 195 University students noted increased stress and anxiety among 71% of the participants (Son et al., 2020). Further, the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) reported 63% of college-aged young adults (18–24 years of age) in the U.S. had elevated depression or anxiety between May and June 2020 (Czeisler et al., 2020). Elevated mental stress among young people may result from inadequate coping skills in the face of COVID-19-related social isolation and boredom; and, even more exacerbated among University students who may have been displaced from the traditional campus setting, leading to learning challenges and grade insecurities (Son et al., 2020; Torales et al., 2020).

Physical activity is often overlooked as a lifestyle habit to preserve mental health. Individuals who are regularly active are less likely to be diagnosed with depression or anxiety (Goodwin, 2003). Moreover, those who met moderate to vigorous physical activity (MVPA) guidelines (defined as either 150 min/week of moderate intensity exercise or 75 min/week of vigorous intensity exercise; or, an equivalent combination of both, by the United States Health and Human Services and World Health Organization) reported a 39% reduction in monthly days of poor mental health (Piercy et al., 2018; Bull et al., 2020). Individuals who were active but did not meet guidelines demonstrated a 25% reduction in days of poor mental health as well, indicating even a small amount of exercise is beneficial (Piercy et al., 2018; Fluetsch et al., 2019). In light of these findings, the World Health Organization (WHO) recently stated that adults should limit the amount of sedentary time and replace it with physical activity of any intensity or type (Bull et al., 2020; Dempsey et al., 2020). These data suggest that

University students who consistently participate in physical activity may be less likely to experience depression and anxiety related to COVID-19 restrictions. Unfortunately, evidence has demonstrated a high prevalence of sedentary behavior among University students (Arias-Palencia et al., 2015). This may inadvertently influence mental health among this group (Lee and Kim, 2019).

The pandemic of COVID-19, which started in December 2019, seriously affected the functioning of basic education institutions in the country and around the world. It became a worldwide health epidemic in which, regardless of age, gender and social status, everybody was literally affected. The world stopped, and when all corporations wound down operations, the economy crashed.

There are numerous coping styles, and the two primary coping strategies addressed are problem- focused coping and emotion-focused coping. The researchers determined what challenges come to students' mind and how it affected in their academic achievement of Grade 10 high school students in

Isabela National High School. The data and evidences were gathered through survey questions, and total enumeration sampling method.

Therefore, the aim of this study was to explore the Coping Mechanisms of Grade 10 Junior High School Learners to sedentary lifestyle in the post-COVID-19 Pandemic.

Research Questions

This study will assess the Coping Mechanisms of Grade 10 Junior High School Learners to Sedentary Lifestyle in the Post-COVID 19 Pandemic: Basis for Recreational Activity Plan. Specifically, the researchers of this study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What are the behavior types of Grade 10 learners of Isabela National High School in handling Post-Covid 19 Pandemic circumstances?
2. What are the preferred coping mechanisms being emphasized by Grade 10 learners as compared to physical activity and sedentary activities?
3. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of the following variables?
 - a. Height
 - b. Weight
 - c. BMI
4. What is the descriptive information in terms of the following:
 - a. Participant characteristics
 - b. COVID-19 related issues
 - c. Participants daily behavior
5. Is there a significant relationship between the coping mechanisms and sedentary lifestyle of Grade 10 learners

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The proponents made use of the descriptive correlational research design since the researchers intended to describe a set of observations or data collected pertaining to the profile variables of the participants and aimed to find out the significant relationship between two variables that were examined in this study which included the coping mechanisms and sedentary lifestyle behaviors.

Locale of the Study

The research setting which will be chosen for this study will be a public National High School in the City of Ilagan, Isabela is located in the heart of the city. A government school will be preferred because government schools in the Philippines are always the first to implement mandates and policies from the government. The research setting was especially chosen because it is a public school.

Selection and Description of Respondents

The population of this study will comprise of one hundred ninety-two (192) grade 10 Learners of Isabela National High School. The data collection will be conducted to these 192 pupils for the School Year 2022-2023 who will represent the population. The 192 respondents of the study will be handled by the researcher in Grade 10.

Data Gathering Procedure

After the proposal was satisfactorily defended and given approval to pursue the study, the researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent of Schools Division of Isabela then she presented it to the district supervisors and school heads. The researcher made use of both the Google form and face to face to float questionnaires to the respondents but had to communicate to the supervisors first about the purpose of the study. The researcher also conducted informal interviews with the teachers and school heads to get other data needed to supplement the information and to clarify vague responses.

The data gathered, collated, tallied and organized in tabular form for analysis and interpretation to provide descriptions of the status, challenges and prospects on teachers' professional development.

Statistical Treatment of Data

Three international guidelines for PA, SB and sleep for adults for health were applied for data analysis: (1) achievement of at least 150 min of moderate-intensity aerobic PA or at least 75 min of vigorous-intensity aerobic PA throughout the week; (2) engagement in <9 h of SB per day for adults; (3) score of sleep quality <5 with sleep

duration between 7 and 9 h. Descriptive information (all and stratified by sex), including participant characteristics, COVID-19 related issues, and participants' daily behaviors, were summarized and reported as means \pm standard deviation (SD) or median (interquartile range) for continuous variables and as proportions of participants for categorical variables. The normality analysis was applied to all variables. Because VPA, MPA, MVPA, walking, and MET min/week are not a normal distribution, the Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test was used to assess the differences between males and females for the above variables. For other variables, independent samples *t*-tests and Chi-Square tests were used for continuous variables and categorical variables, respectively. The change in participants' daily behaviors (e.g., PA, SB, and sleep) was determined using paired sample *t*-tests and shown as means \pm SD. All statistical tests were performed using SPSS for Windows, version 24.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

3.1. Descriptive Statistics of Participant

Behavior Type	Percent
Watch tv/movies (Netflix, Soap Operas, Vlogs)	54
Physical activity	48
Favorite hobbies (gaming, crafts, checking social media etc.)	46
Spending time with family/ friends	40
Relaxation (bath, ho waterbottle, etc.)	31
Diet/ eating well	29
Fulfilling my food cravings	25
Mindfulness/ meditation	19
Alcohol	18
Yoga/ stretching	17
Having a cry	17
Prescribed medications	14
Seeing a professional therapist / doctor	8
Something else	9
Nothing helps me to cope with	1

Data collected by the proponent that Grade 10 Learners are less likely to use physical activity as compared to more sedentary activities (e.g., watching TV) as a coping mechanism for stress or anxiety reduction. Given broad “stay-at-home” directions, it might be expected that individuals are more likely to resort to passive indoor leisure vs. active leisure to handle stress in general— pandemic or not. More concerning is a potential reluctance to consider physical activity as a primary coping measure. This risks shifting an already inactive population even lower. Correlates of using physical activity as a coping mechanism are consistent with prior research— younger, more educated, and those of

higher socio-economic status (Cairney et al., 2014). These individuals may have better access to physical activity resources (whether online or in their personal homes) and more time (e.g., fewer family responsibilities). Further, during times of social isolation, Grade 10 are reporting placing less emphasis on engaging in physical activity compared to connecting with family or friends and relaxing/distressing. The current COVID19 crisis has created a “new normal,” with less emphasis placed on physical activity (in comparison to screen use, socialization) by a significant minority of Canadians. The fact that 20% of respondents reported less emphasis on physical activity during the pandemic suggests that the social distancing and isolation regulations may have put new barriers in place for some to engage in physical activity compared to post-pandemic times.

COPING MECHANISMS	MORE EMPHASIS	THE SAME AMOUNT OF EMPHASIS	LESS EMPHASIS
Connecting with family/friends	36	49	15
Relaxation/ Destressing	35	60	5
Creative time/hobbies	34	57	9
Reading	33	57	10
Binging shows	32	51	17
Physical activity	28	51	20
Eating well	25	55	9
Mindfulness/ meditation	15	70	15

The findings suggest a potential disconnect between participating in physical activity as a strategy to support social connection and stress management and how Grade 10 are coping with stress in particular. While it is possible that people are choosing lesser effective strategies to deal with the consequences of COVID-19 (possibly due to personal interest or boredom), it is important that individuals remain informed of the compounding effects behaviors like excess screen-viewing can have on the mind and body, potentially exacerbating symptoms of poor mental health (Madhav et al., 2017).

Consequently, we believe a potential role exists for social marketing initiatives to address this disconnect and communicate more explicitly the mental health benefits of physical activity. In the context of physical distancing measures, this may take the form of focusing on family or household co-participation in physical activity. Sharing evidence about the stress management benefits of physical activity may also be beneficial. Such messaging also needs to convey the “how to” and develop individual’s self-efficacy to engage in physical activity for mental health benefits. Consequently, health communications are likely to be less than optimally beneficial if they are not supported by parallel initiatives that support access to opportunities for physical activity while allowing for physical distancing (Institute of Medicine, 2015). For example, these initiatives could include temporary reallocation of roadway space and keeping expansive green spaces

open. In dense urban environments, initiatives could include reallocating traffic lanes to allow for cycling and walking with social distancing possible. In response to the COVID-19 pandemic, coupled with the growing incidence of stress, anxiety, and depression among Canadians (Rajkumar, 2020), many other health-based organizations have begun to tailor their communication and marketing efforts to better reflect the current social and environmental climate.

A total 192 participants were included in data analysis. The characteristics of the participants are shown in Table 1. Based on the WHO's recommendations for Asian adults, 12.2% and 23.3% of the males and females were overweight, respectively.

Participant Characteristics for cross-sectional study and stratified by sex

Table 1	Mean ±SD			
	All	Males	Females	P Value
Height (cm)	165.6 ±8.3	173.2 ±6.1	160.8 ±5.5	<0.01
Weight (kg)	57.0 ±10.1	64.3 ±10.0	52.4 ±7.0	<0.01
BMI (kg/m ²)	20.7 ±2.6	21.4 ±2.9	20.3 ±2.4	<0.01

BMI: Body Mass Index, SD: Standard Deviation

Lifestyle Behavior during COVID-19 Pandemic

Sedentary Lifestyle behaviors (e.g., PA, SB, and sleep) are presented in Table 2, where 30% of participants met the PA guideline, and more than half of the participants (57.8%) did not engage in any VPA during the COVID-19 pandemic. In total, 70% of participants reported that their PA level decreased since the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic. Compared to males, engagement in computer/video games was lower while engagement in computer/paper work and arts and crafts was higher in females. Despite the fact that females had a significantly longer mean sleep duration than males (8.7 ± 1.2 vs. 8.5 ± 1.2, $p < 0.05$), more male participants met the sleep guidelines than females (46.5 vs. 38.1, $p < 0.05$).

Participants' Lifestyle behaviors for cross-sectional study and stratified by sex

Table 2	Mean ±SD or %	Or Median (IQR)		
Variables	All	Males	Females	P Value
PA				
Walking (min/day)	17.1 (28.6)	17.1(27.1)	12.85(28.6)	0.07

Moderate PA (min/day)	2.9 (11.4)	2.85(12.9)	2.85(10.4)	0.30
Vigorous PA (min/day)	0.0 (8.6)	0.0(10.0)	0.0(8.6)	0.16
Moderate to Vigorous (min/day)	8.6 (25.0)	8.6(25.7)	5.7(0.7)	0.18
Total Energy Expenditure (MET min/week)	792.0(1398.0)	864.25.7	792.0(1230.0)	0.07
Change of PA Level				0.05
Increase	16.5	12.2	19.2	-
No Change	11.3	10.6	11.7	-
Decrease	72.3	77.1	69.2	-
Meet PA Guidelines	29.6	30.2	29.3	0.80
SB				
TV/DVD (h/day)	1.7±1.5	1.6±1.5	1.8±1.5	0.26
Computer/ Video games (h/day)	1.4±1.6	1.9±1.8	1.1±1.4	<0.01
Sitting, Listening to music (h/day)	1.1±1.3	1.1±1.4	1.1±1.3	0.65
Sitting Talking on Phone (h/day)	0.8±1.2	0.9±1.3	0.8±1.2	0.90
Computer / Paper work (h/day)	3.1±1.8	2.9±1.8	3.3±1.8	<0.01
Reading Books (h/day)	0.5±0.9	0.5±0.9	0.6±0.9	0.39
Play Musical Instrument (h/day)	0.2±0.5	0.2±0.4	0.2±0.6	0.52
Doing arts and crafts (h/day)	0.2±0.5	0.1±0.4	0.2±0.6	<0.01
Sitting for transport (h/day)	0.4±0.6	0.4±0.7	0.4±0.5	0.15
Daily SB (h/day)	9.4±3.0	9.4±3.2	9.5±3.0	0.77
Meet SB Guidelines	42.5	44.1	41.5	0.97
Sleep				
Sleep Duration (h/day)	8.6±1.2	8.5±1.2	8.7±1.2	0.02
Sleep Quality	5.2±2.5	4.9±2.3	5.3±2.6	0.07
Meet Sleep Guidelines	41.4	46.5	38.1	0.04
Change in Sleep Quality				0.07
Better than Usual	18.4	20.8	16.8	
The same as usual	43.9	46.9	42.0	
Worse than usual	37.7	32.2	41.2	

Changes in Lifestyle Behaviors after COVID-19 Outbreak

The changes in lifestyle behaviors in participants from the longitudinal study are presented in [Figure 1](#). After the COVID-19 outbreak, all PA levels, including VPA (before vs. during COVID-19, 9.5 ± 12.5 vs. 6.0 ± 11.6 , $p < 0.05$), MPA (11.2 ± 16.0 vs. 5.5 ± 8.7 , $p < 0.01$), and walking (39.7 ± 30.7 vs. 19.8 ± 24.5 , $p < 0.01$), were significantly declined, while both time spent in SB (7.8 ± 3.2 vs. 10.0 ± 3.2 , $p < 0.01$) and sleep duration (7.7 ± 1.0 vs. 8.4 ± 1.2 , $p < 0.01$) significantly increased. A lower percentage of participants met the guidelines for PA (50.0% vs. 20.0%), SB (54.3% vs. 40.0%), and sleep (67.1% vs. 57.1%) after the COVID-19 outbreak. When considering the SB by types of activities, engagement in TV/DVD (0.9 ± 0.8 vs. 1.7 ± 1.4 , $p < 0.01$) and computer/paper work (2.2 ± 1.7 vs. 3.1 ± 2.0 , $p < 0.01$) was significantly higher and sitting time during transportation (0.7 ± 0.7 vs. 0.4 ± 0.6 , $p < 0.01$) was significantly lower during COVID-19 than before the epidemic.

Figure 1

3.4. COVID-19 related Issues

Table 3 Variables	%			
Main Sources of Information	All	Males	Females	P Value
Newspaper or TV	37.4	33.5	39.9	
Government websites	2.4	1.2	3.1	
Friends	1.0	0.8	1.0	
Facebook/Twitter/Instagram/Youtube	59.3	64.5	56.0	
Home quarantine/compulsory quarantine				.35
Yes	7.1	5.7	8.0	
No	92.1	93.1	91.5	
Prefer not to say	0.8	1.2	0.5	
Contracting Covid-19 myself				-0.01
Not at all concerned	3.2	5.7	1.6	
Slightly Concerned	13.6	15.5	12.4	
Somewhat concerned	22.5	25.3	20.7	
Moderately concerned	43.1	37.6	46.6	
Extremely concerned	17.6	15.9	18.7	
Family members contracting COVID-19				0.02

COVID-19 related issues are presented in [Table 3](#), including the main sources of information, concern of contracting COVID-19, and prevention strategies. Generally, females had greater concern for contracting COVID-19 themselves and for their family members contracting COVID-19. Therefore, females engaged more in COVID-19

prevention strategies, such as wearing a face mask and avoiding restaurants, gyms, and shops, compared to males.

Table 3	%			
COVID-19 related issues for cross-sectional study and stratified by sex				
Hand-washing with soap	-	-	-	0.07
Always	55.6	49.8	59.3	-
Often	32.5	35.5	30.6	-
Sometimes	9.4	11.0	8.3	-
Rarely	2.2	2.9	1.8	-
Never	0.3	0.8	0.0	-
Wearing Face mask	-	-	-	0.02
Always	88.9	84.9	91.5	-
Often	8.1	9.4	7.3	-
Sometimes	2.1	3.7	1.0	-
Rarely	0.5	0.8	0.3	-
Never	0.5	1.2	0.0	-
Avoiding Restaurants/gyms/shops	-	-	-	0.02
Always	35.0	28.6	39.1	-
Often	34.2	34.7	33.9	-
Sometimes	24.4	27.3	22.5	-
Rarely	5.5	8.2	3.9	-
Never	0.8	1.2	0.5	-

This is the study, to the best of the researcher’s knowledge, to investigate the Coping Mechanisms of Grade 10 learners through PA levels, time spent in SB, and sleep in young adults after the COVID-19 pandemic and the changes in these sedentary lifestyle behaviors after the COVID-19 outbreak in Ilagan National High School. The major findings of this study were that engagement in all PA behaviors significantly declined while time spent in SB and sleep duration significantly increased following the COVID-19 outbreak.

The finding of a decrease in all types of PA (i.e., MPA, VPA and walking) after the COVID-19 outbreak.

This result of this study is in corroboration with the study of Moore (2020) which is consistent with a recent national survey in Canada, which reported a significant decline in all physical activities in children and adolescents.

The cross-sectional analysis also revealed the low volume of PA that participants engaged in after the COVID-19 pandemic, with an average of 3 min/day spent in MPA and 17 min/day walking.

Similarly, Xiang et al. 2020 reported that children and adolescents engaged in 105 min per week during the COVID-19 pandemic in Shanghai. The low volume of PA undertaken by participants may be due to social distancing (e.g., cancellation of all team sports training and competitions and the closure of public leisure facilities and gymnasiums), working from home and concern of the threat posed by COVID-19 in Hong Kong. Furthermore, the limited living space in Hong Kong, which is smaller than in other Asian cities, including Tokyo and Singapore, may further restrict the opportunities for young adults to exercise at home.

The total time spent in SB during the waking day was significantly higher during COVID-19 than prior to the outbreak. This is consistent with a national survey, which reported that daily sitting time increased from 5 to 8 h (28.6%) per day during home confinement.

Similarly, children and adolescents in both Shanghai and Canada engaged in more than 5 h of screen time per day Xiang (2020).

This may be partially explained by young adults engaging in social distancing by staying home, and online teaching, which subsequently resulted in prolonged screen time, such as elevated time spent watching TV, playing computer games, and online teaching. Specifically, students spent less time on transportation, less time in P.E. class, and the majority of the academic term in screen time during the online teaching period. Consequently, we also found that time spent in both TV/DVD and computer/paper work significantly increased while sitting time for transport decreased following the COVID-19 outbreak.

Increased screen time, which was reported in this study, has been previously shown to be accompanied by prolonged sedentary bouts without interruption, which have a more negative impact on health outcomes [Carson and Wong, 2020]. Interventions that increase PA while decrease SB in young adults after the COVID-19 pandemic are warranted, especially for inactive individuals as they are more likely to become less active after the COVID-19 pandemic (Lesser and Nienhuis, 2020).

For instance, simple home-based exercises, such as body resistance training or high-intensity interval training (HIIT), can be applied to this population. Appropriate health education and behavior interventions via online platforms can also be developed during this pandemic, as more than 70% of participants reported that their engagement in PA had significantly decreased during the COVID-19 pandemic. Interestingly, one study reported that women who spent more time exercising outdoors had better mental and general health than those who were not [Colley and Bushnik, 2020]. Moreover, maintaining regular PA during the COVID-19 pandemic is important for preventing future chronic health conditions due to a sedentary lifestyle (Jakobsson and Malm,2020).

The COVID-19 pandemic brings significant disruptions to daily routines. With a more flexible schedule due to the closure of schools, colleges, universities and businesses, participants had significantly longer sleep duration during the pandemic.

Of particular interest is that 37% of participants reported having poorer sleep quality after the COVID-19 pandemic. Since poor sleep is highly correlated with stress, poor sleep quality reported by participants may be due to the stress induced by the threat of COVID-19. Notably, 40.7% of Grade 10 learners reported a negative change in sleep since the onset of COVID-19 because of change in exercise behaviors, and employment and relationship concerns. Thus, maintaining a regular sleep routine during the COVID-19 pandemic is essential. Furthermore, the effect of COVID-19 on sleep and mental health among young adults warrants further investigation.

Individual behaviors of young adults have been changed in response to the threat posed by COVID-19. Based on our results, 90% of Grade 10 learners reported that they always wear a face mask when leaving home, and only 0.3% of participants reported never wearing a face mask.

Previous research has shown that wearing face-masks during exercise causes a significant increase in physiological demand (Wong, 2020). This may influence PA or exercise behaviors of individuals. Similarly, a recent study found that 99% of participants reported wearing face masks when leaving home (Cowling, 2020).

In addition, 85% of participants reported that they always or often wash their hands with soap. When the severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) occurred in Hong Kong in 2003, the proportion of face mask use and washing hands among adults was 79% and 82%, respectively (Leung, 2004).

Interestingly, females showed more concerns about contracting COVID-19 themselves or their family members contracting it, and therefore engaged in more prevention strategies that included always wearing a face mask and avoiding restaurants/gyms/shops than males, which may lead to gender-difference in reduced outdoor activities during the pandemic.

One major strength of this study is that both cross-sectional and longitudinal analyses were applied. Secondly, there was a relatively large sample size in the cross-sectional analysis. Thirdly, three behaviors (PA, SB, and sleep), which occupy a large proportion of time in individuals over 24 h were assessed in the current study.

The limitations of this study include the use of subjective measurements to assess PA, SB and sleep, which are associated with increased risk of bias. Though all the questionnaires used in this study have been previously validated, objective measurement, such as the use of an accelerometer, would be more accurate in assessing PA and SB in participants.

Conclusions

Low PA levels, high amount of time spent on SBs, and long sleep duration were identified in young adults during the COVID-19 pandemic, with less than half of the participants meeting any of the recommended guidelines for PA, SB or sleep. There was also a significant reduction in PA behaviors and a significant increase in SB and the sleep duration of young adults following the outbreak of COVID-19. These findings may have important public health implications and provide evidence for future intervention studies and a basis for recreational studies.

The fact that 20% of respondents reported less emphasis on physical activity during the pandemic suggests that the social distancing and isolation regulations may have put new barriers in place for some to engage in physical activity compared to post-pandemic times.

Social distancing and isolation regulations may have put new barriers in place for some to engage in physical activity compared to post-pandemic times. engagement in all PA behaviors significantly declined while time spent in SB and sleep duration significantly increased following the COVID-19 outbreak.

It is the finding of this study that there is a decrease in all types of PA (i.e., MPA, VPA and walking) after the COVID-19 outbreak.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following are hereby recommended for considerations.

1. Teachers and school leaders to encourage active lifestyle by incorporating physical activity into daily lives at schools, including walking to school, launching fitness dance programs and active recreational activities.
2. PE Teachers to strategize on how to break barriers around active lifestyle by opening trainings and seminar workshops free or affordable.
3. Improve interconnection with the lesson and resources on healthy sleep habits, such as keeping a regular sleep schedule, and responsible utilization of gadgets.
4. Develop technology-based interventions in alignment with the specific needs and preferences of young adults.
5. Provide opportunities for social interaction and support networks; these may play a very important role in promoting physical activity and general wellbeing.
6. Give access to school governing councils and stakeholders on mental health resources and support, in the ways of counseling, stress management techniques, and social activities.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher made sure that during the conduct of the study, the following ethical concerns were followed to necessitate safe, anti-fraud, deliberate, and careful undertakings in the study:

1. The researcher, through proper communications, asked permission from the Division Office, and other concerned offices for the study;
2. The researcher also acknowledged the Department of Education and the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan for allowing her to conduct the study;
3. The researcher informed the respondents of the study through letters and a short orientation to the study. Data and information gathered were treated with utmost respect and confidentiality;
4. The researcher, properly cited gathered information and other relevant studies from authors, books, or any publications through proper citation.

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